

A Study to Assess the Knowledge & Attitude Regarding TECHO PLUS Among ASHA Workers Are Working Under PHC Shirur

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ABSTRACT

Background: Accredited social health activists (ASHAs) are government instituted community health workers as part of the National Rural Health Mission. The purpose of this study was to assess the knowledge and attitude of ASHAs regarding TECHO PLUS. **Methods:** A cross sectional survey was carried out among 60 ASHA workers. A self-constructed, by using prepared tool based on TECHO PLUS knowledge and attitude among ASHA worker was translated into regional language. **Result:** The above tables assess knowledge and attitude regarding TECHO Plus among ASHA worker. The range value is 160, the mean value is 23.03, the minimum value is 40, the maximum value is 160, the standard deviation is 0.82, and the means percentage is 52.52%. The calculated chi square value based on knowledge of ASHA worker 3.95 (P value 0.04) suggests there is a significant association between their age in year and chi square value of 6.11 (P value 0.01) suggested there is significant association between their marital status regarding TECHO PLUS among ASHA worker. **Conclusion:** Study clearly indicates that the knowledge of most of the ASHA workers is at an average level and there is a need to revise and update it from time to time. On job trainings of the ASHAs should be in process to develop necessary knowledge and skills with recent updates.

Keywords: ASHA worker, knowledge, attitude and TECHO PLUS

INTRODUCTION

Activity of ASHA [Accredited Social Health Activist] is one of the key components in the National rural Health Mission. They provide information to the community on determinants of health such as nutrition, basic sanitation, hygienic practices, healthy living & working condition, information on existing health services and need for the timely utilization of health and family welfare services and they are an important link between the community and health facilities.¹ ASHAs are pivotal in connecting the community with the healthcare system, fostering preventive health measures, and contributing to the overall well-being of the populace. This paper assess the knowledge Skills and Attitude level aiming to shed light on the path forward for enhancing the efficacy of ASHAs to deliver better public health services in rural India.² Neonatal period is from birth to 28 days and neonatal deaths are deaths, commencing at birth and ending in 28 completed days. Every year in India over one million newborns

die before they complete their first month of life, accounting for 30% of the world's neonatal deaths. Preterm, sepsis and intra-partum causes like birth asphyxia, congenital malformation and pneumonia.³ The Government of India launched National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) in 2005 to address the health needs of rural population, especially the vulnerable section of the society. With the launch of NRHM, the government of India proposed Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA) to act as the interface between the community and the public health system. One of the key components of the National Rural Health Mission is to provide every village in the country with a trained female community health activist known as Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA) who is selected from the same village and cover the population of 1000.⁴ The ASHA workers knowledge toward oral health to a great extent influences the community as they can extend health education at the first contact in the community. Literature on the Early Childhood caries knowledge of community health care workers is scarce.

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Therefore, a study was to conduct to assess the knowledge of ASHA workers on early childhood caries.⁵

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A descriptive research design was used in the study. A **simple** random technique was used to obtain 60 samples working under PHC shirur Bagalkote. Data were collected using a individual topic and structured questionnaire to evaluate Knowledge and attitude of asha worker. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Sources of data:

The present study data were collected from asha worker. A descriptive survey approach is designed when the purpose of the study is to describe the prevalence or incidence of phenomena or to estimate the value of phenomena for a population. In the present study, the main aim is to evaluate the knowledge and attitude of asha woker.

Research Design: A descriptive study is a research in which a onetime evaluation of knowledge attitude of asha worker working under shirur PHC Bagalkote the research design defines the population, sample, size, variables, data collection tools and methods, and data analysis plan.

VARIABLES:

Dependent variable: In this study, Asha workers are the dependent variable.

Independent variable: In this study, independent variables are the factors of knowledge and attitude such as age, sex, education status then feelings working response.

Socio variables: It consists of 07 items: Age in year, marital status, Work experience, Education status, Religion, Number of wards and Range of population.

Setting of study: The study was conducted at shirur PHC, Bagalkot.

Population: Asha worker working under shirur PHC, Bagalkot.

Sample and sample technique: we chose 60 asha workers and used stratified random sampling techniques conducted at shirur PHC, Bagalkot.

Data Collection Tool: Data collection tools are the procedures or instruments used by the researcher to observe or measure the key variable in the research problem. Individual topic and semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect the data in the present study.

Procedure for Data Collection:

Data collected from 05/07/2025 to 18/07/2025. Data collection was carried out in 3 phases: the first phase was data collection regarding socio-demographic factors and knowledge assessment of asha worker. Second phase: data collection regarding knowledge of asha worker Third phase: data collection regarding the attitude of Asha workers. Data collected from all asha worker based on their socio-demographic factors and used questionnaire and individual topic among asha worker.

Ethical Consideration:

Ethical approval was obtained from B.V.V.S. Institute of Nursing Sciences and Institutional Ethics Committee, Bagalkot. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Result: A study was conducted to determine that there was significant association ($P < 0.04$) between age in year and knowledge of asha worker.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data analysis is the systematic organization and synthesis of research data and the testing of research hypotheses by using the collected data. The data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

- Demographic data was analyzed using frequency and percentage distribution.
- The mean and standard deviation were used to assess the knowledge and attitude of asha worker.
- A chi-square test was used to find an association between the knowledge and attitude regarding TECHO Plus among Asha worker.

Result: The above tables assess knowledge and attitude regarding TECHO Plus among ashaworker. The range value is 80, the mean value is 23.03, the minimum value is 40, the maximum value is 160, the standard deviation is 0.82, and the means percentage is 52.52%. The calculated chi square value based on knowledge of ashaworker 3.95 (P value 0.04) suggests there is a significant association between their age in year and chi square value of 6.11 (P value

0.01) suggested there is significant association between their marital status regarding TECHO plus among ashaworker. The calculated chi square value of 4.54 (P value 0.03) suggests there is a significant association between their Education status and chi square value based on attitude of ashaworker of 3.01 (P value 0.04) suggested there is significant association between their range of population regarding TECHO plus among ashaworker.

Table No. 1. Distribution and description of participants according to their socio- demographic factors.

Sl.no	Attributes	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age in year	• 18-25	03	05%
		• 26-35	23	38.33%
		• 36-45	26	43.33%
		• 46-55	08	13.33%
2.	Marital status	✓ Unmarried	10	16.66%
		✓ Married	40	66.66%
		✓ Widow	10	16.66%
3.	Work experience	○ < 2 years	15	25%
		○ > 2 years	45	75%
4.	Education status	▪ 10 th Standard	34	56.66%
		▪ PUC	24	40%
		▪ Graduation	02	03.33%
5.	Religion	▪ Hindu	44	73.33%
		▪ Muslim	14	23.33%
		▪ Christian	02	03.33%
6.	Number of wards	○ 1	45	75%
		○ 2	15	25%
7.	Range of population	• <10000	43	71.66%
		• 15 to 20000	15	25%
		• >20000	02	03.33%

Description of ashaworker based on their categories.

Distribution of the sample according to age total 60 workers. 03(05%) were 18 to 25 years old, 23(38.33%) were 26 to 35 years old, 26(43.33%) were 36 to 45 years old and 13(16.25%) 46 to 55 years old. 10(16.66%) were from unmarried, 40(66.66%) were married and 10(16.66%) were widow of their marital status. Next work experience 15(25%) were >2 years,

45(75%) were <2years. then Education status 34(56.66%) were 10th standard, 24(40%) were PUC, 02(03.33%) were graduation, next religion 44(73.33%) were received Hindu, 14(23.33%) were Muslim and 02(03.33%) were Christian. Then number of wards 45(75%) were 1st ward and 15(25%) were 2nd ward. Next range of population 43(71.66%) were <10000 population, 15(25%) were 15 to 20000 population and 02(03.33%) were >2000 population.

Table No. 2. Distribution and Description of level of assessment regarding TECHO plus among ashaworker N=60

Sl.no	Level of assessment	Frequency	Percentage
1	Excellent	6	10%
2	Good	20	33.33%
3	Average	24	40%
4	Poor	10	16.66%

According to the above table, out of 60 workers, 10% have excellent knowledge regarding TECHO plus among asha worker. 16.66% have poor knowledge, 40% have average knowledge, and 33.33% have good knowledge and

Table No. 3. Distribution and description of sample based on Mean, range, standard deviation regarding TECHO plus among asha worker N=60

Range	Mean	Min	Max	Sd	Mean %
80	23.03	40	160	0.82	52.52%

The above tables assess knowledge and attitude regarding TECHO Plus among asha worker. The range value is 80, the mean value is 23.03, the

minimum value is 40, the maximum value is 160, the standard deviation is 0.82, and the means percentage is 52.52%.

Table No. 4. Chi-square test shows an association between knowledge and their socio-demographic factors regarding TECHO plus among asha worker N=60

Sl.no	Chi-square	Df	P value	Association
1	3.95	1	0.04	Significant
2	6.11	1	0.01	Significant
3	0.22	1	0.63	NS
4	0.06	1	0.80	NS
5	0.41	1	0.52	NS
6	0.96	1	0.32	NS
7	0.11	1	0.74	NS

$\alpha = 0.05$

Results related to assessing the knowledge and their socio-demographic factors regarding TECHO plus among asha worker

The calculated chi square value of 3.95 (P value 0.04) suggests there is a significant association between their age in year and chi square value of 6.11 (P value 0.01) suggested there is significant association between their marital status regarding TECHO plus among asha worker.

Table No. 5. Chi-square test shows an association between attitude and their socio-demographic factors regarding TECHO plus among asha worker N=60

Sl.no	Chi-square	Df	P value	Association
1	0.03	1	0.86	NS
2	0.08	1	0.77	NS
3	0.05	1	0.82	NS
4	4.54	1	0.03	Significant
5	0.08	1	0.77	NS
6	0.82	1	0.36	NS
7	3.08	1	0.07	Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Results related to assessing the attitude regarding TECHO plus among asha worker

The calculated chi square value of 4.54 (P value 0.03) suggests there is a significant association between their Education status and chi square value of 3.01 (P

value 0.04) suggested there is significant association between their range of population regarding TECHO plus among asha worker.

DISCUSSION:

To assess the knowledge & attitude regarding TECHO PLUS among ASHA workers. A cross-

sectional descriptive design was used. The study was conducted at PHC Shirur Hospital, Bagalkot. Almost 86.2% of ASHA workers had improper knowledge regarding new born care. Nearly 70% knew the causes of diarrhea but 91.5% of them had no idea about signs of the dehydration. Study conducted by Saxena S et al found that mostly 96.9% ASHA knew that breastfeeding should be given first to the newborn and 95.3% ASHA were known that breastfeeding should be initiated within one hour of delivery and 71.9%.⁷ For instance, 100% knew that early detection reduces cancer progression, and 90% were aware of cancer risk factors. However, awareness about specific screening methods was lower, with only 16.7% knowing about breast self-examination and 10% about mammograms.⁸ A large proportion of the ASHAs commonly cited vomiting (73%), swelling of hands and feet (72%) followed by paleness, abdominal pain, body pain/backache, convulsions, excessive bleeding.⁹

CONCLUSION:

Study clearly indicates that the knowledge of most of the ASHA workers is at an average level and there is a need to revise and update it from time to time. On job trainings of the ASHAs should be in process to develop necessary knowledge and skills with recent updates.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVE:

ASHA workers had average knowledge regarding TECHO PLUS like care of new born, antenatal, intra natal, post-natal, breast feeding technique, immunization, various health services and vulnerable groups. They need to update, attend the meeting and conduct skill-based program based on their needs and problems of the people.

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